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Abstract

The Uniform Civil Code (UCC) debate in India revolves around implementing comprehensive laws to replace existing personal laws across various religious faiths. Despite its aspirational nature in the Indian Constitution, the issue has gained momentum, leading to discussions at both state and national levels. This article presents the historical context and judicial interpretations, the debate surrounding gender equality, and the concerns of tribal communities. Various viewpoints on addressing the UCC have been presented, emphasising constructive dialogue and unity among citizens. This article also highlights the need for thoughtful consideration and inclusive discussions to address the complex and contentious issue of the Indian UCC.

Keywords: Uniform Civil Code (UCC), India, Gender equality, Cultural diversity, Inclusive dialogue, Justice, Religious Laws, Tribes.

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Introduction

The Indian Uniform Civil Code (UCC) refers to a comprehensive set of laws that will replace existing customary laws across different religious faiths, covering critical aspects such as marriage, divorce, inheritance, adoption, and maintenance. Within the Indian Constitution, the UCC falls under non-justiciable Directive Principles of State Policy, signifying its aspirational nature rather than being enforceable through the judicial courts (Economic Times online, 2023).

Despite the Law Commission expressing in 2018 that the UCC was not an immediate necessity or desirability, the issue has recently gained significant momentum, primarily influenced by Prime Minister Narendra Modi's strong advocacy for its implementation. The Prime Minister emphasises the need for a unified legal framework that applies uniformly to all citizens, promoting harmonious family functioning and national integration (Mohan J, 2023).

Uttarakhand has also taken proactive steps in this direction, forming an expert committee headed by Justice (Retired) Ranjana Prakash Desai. The committee's primary goal is to facilitate the implementation of the Uniform Civil Code and assess the existing laws governing personal matters for the state's residents (Ramachandran, 2023). Additionally, the Allahabad High Court has also entered the discussion, urging the Central government to initiate the process of implementing the UCC nationwide (Rashid, 2021).

Historical Context

Throughout history, implementing a UCC in India drew inspiration from similar codes developed in European nations during the 19th and early 20th centuries. Notably, the French Code of 1804 was a prominent example, replacing various customary and statutory laws with a comprehensive uniform code. Colonial endeavours influenced this concept of "civilising" the nation in the West. However, the First War of Indian Independence in 1857 sent a clear message to the British rulers that altering India's social fabric and overriding personal codes governing aspects like marriage, divorce, maintenance, adoption, and succession would not be tolerated (Mehrotra, 2022).

After gaining independence, the Partition and its aftermath, marked by communal discord, further solidified the resistance to dismantling personal laws. As a result, the UCC was accommodated as a Directive Principle in the Indian Constitution rather than being imposed as a justiciable law. The movement for the Uniform Civil Code (UCC) in India once gained momentum in the 1990s, primarily championed by the Communist Party, attracting individuals seeking comprehensive reforms.

Judicially, it is stated that the Supreme Court has consistently emphasised the significance of having a UCC in various cases, starting from the landmark Shah Bano Begum case to more recent instances like Shayara Bano versus the Union of India, which declared the practice of triple talaq unconstitutional (Mehrotra, 2022).

In the Shah Bano case, former Chief Justice YV Chandrachud stressed that the Parliament should outline the contours of a standard civil code, as it fosters national harmony and equality before the law. In cases like Sarla Mudgal versus the Union of India, the court urged the government to adopt a UCC based on the model of the Hindu code to protect the rights of abused women and promote national solidarity (Mehrotra, 2022).

More recent cases have also highlighted the need for a UCC to address issues of succession and guardianship. The Supreme Court's stance has consistently emphasised the convenience and equity a uniform civil code can bring.

The current ruling political party, the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP), has pledged to draft a UCC that harmonises traditional values with modern principles, recognising that gender equality cannot be achieved without such a comprehensive legal framework. As the discourse continues, India faces the challenge of embracing a UCC that respects its diverse heritage while advancing the rights and welfare of all its citizens, particularly women.

The UCC debate is gaining traction again, bringing to the forefront the challenge of balancing individual religious practices with the larger goal of fostering unity and equal rights for all citizens.

The Objective of the UCC: Advantages and Challenges

Supporters of the Uniform Civil Code (UCC) argue that its implementation will foster the integration of India by providing a shared platform for diverse communities. Prime Minister Narendra Modi emphasised the need for a UCC, highlighting that differential laws for family members within the same household could compromise family harmony and the nation's functioning. The Supreme Court has also expressed its displeasure with the absence of a single set of personal laws for all citizens, urging the adoption of a UCC in various cases. Experts like Kerala Governor Arif Mohammed Khan and Zakia Soman advocate for the UCC to ensure gender justice, offering equal rights and protection to women from various religious backgrounds. They contend that the UCC will create a uniform law for everyone, promoting national integration and justice (Shukla, 2023).

Opponents of the UCC argue that its implementation could violate the constitutional right to freely practice one's chosen religion, as personal laws

are tied to religious communities. They believe applying the principle of 'one nation, one law' to personal matters could lead to enforcing Hindu practices on other communities, potentially undermining their cultural and religious rights. The 21st Law Commission has recommended reforming family laws across religions to ensure gender equity rather than a blanket UCC, recognising the importance of preserving diversity and accommodating differences in a vibrant democratic system. Experts like Faizan Mustafa and the Rashtriya Adivasi Ekta Parishad emphasise the need to consider India's diverse and multicultural society when proposing a UCC, as uniformity may not be conducive to justice for all communities (Shukla, 2023).

Women and the Uniform Civil Code: While looking at the UCC from a gendered perspective, the article by *The Wire* (2023) mentioned Dr Sarasu Esther Thomas, a distinguished law professor at the National Law School of India University, Bangalore, who asserted that achieving gender justice does not necessarily require a UCC. She proposed implementing minor uniform laws that promote gender justice instead of attempting to overhaul all laws simultaneously, which may not be practically feasible. One such successful implementation she cited is the Domestic Violence Act, which applies uniformly to all women, irrespective of their personal laws, making it a form of a uniform civil code within a specific domain.

Additionally, Zakia Soman, a founding member of the rights group Bharatiya Muslim Mahila Andolan, expressed concern that Muslim women have been disadvantaged due to the absence of codified personal laws. In contrast, Hindu women have benefited from the Hindu Code Bill. She highlighted Muslim women's disparity and discrimination, emphasising the need for codified Muslim laws or a UCC to address their rights.

This article also opined that even the Hindu Code Bill, passed in the 1950s and includes laws on marriage, succession, and inheritance, is not entirely gender-just, as it still discriminates based on gender.

Flavia Agnes, an Indian women's rights lawyer with expertise in marital, divorce, and property law, in a 2016 interview, stated that promoting reforms from within and utilising judicial intervention are more effective and meaningful ways to empower women from minority communities. She points to the Goa law on polygamy, which the UN lists as discriminatory against women, despite being under a uniform civil code influenced by the Portuguese civil procedure code since 1939.

The crucial lesson from this is that merely enacting a uniform law does not guarantee gender justice. Instead, Agnes advocates for a focus on transforming diverse personal laws to ensure gender equality. This stance reflects her position, emphasising the importance of context-sensitive reforms

that respect religious diversity while prioritising women's rights (Naskar, 2016).

Tribal Communities and the Uniform Civil Code: The proposal for a UCC is also viewed as a concern towards the protective provisions embedded in the Indian Constitution for the tribal communities in India. Tribes, comprising both linguistic and religious minorities, follow customary laws that are not explicitly tied to religion. The UCC directly conflicts with the constitutional provisions in the sixth schedule for states like Assam, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Tripura, and the constitutional statuses of Nagaland and Mizoram under 371A and 371G, respectively (Zaman, 2023). Critics argue that implementing a common civil code would erode these communities' special privileges, granting them a measure of autonomy to follow their customary laws.

Numerous leaders and civil society groups in states like Meghalaya, Nagaland, Mizoram, and Sikkim have voiced their worries about how the UCC might impact their unique cultures and identities. They firmly believe that their customary laws, deeply rooted in history and intertwined with their social fabric, would suffer adverse consequences under the proposed uniform code.

Leaders from various Northeast states, including Chief Minister Conrad Sangma of Meghalaya, along with representatives of tribal bodies, have emphasised the need to safeguard the region's diverse cultural and traditional practices. They argued that a one-size-fits-all approach would be inappropriate for India's multicultural and multi-ethnic society.

Due to the escalating opposition and concerns expressed by the Northeast region, the Central government appears to be reevaluating its position. During a parliamentary committee meeting, there were suggestions that tribal populations in the Northeast and other regions should be exempted from the purview of the uniform civil code. The shift indicates a recognition of the necessity to address the sensitivities and demands of the diverse communities in the region (Zaman, 2023).

Implementing a Uniform Civil Code (UCC) to attain gender equality should be critically re-examined. Instead, a more considerate and balanced approach towards social inclusion and gender justice is required. Merely using the pretext of equality or the greater good to bypass protective laws would undermine the equal opportunities guaranteed in the Constitution for vulnerable and marginalised groups.

To truly address the issue, acknowledging the significance of these protective measures and adopting a more thoughtful strategy is necessary for India to move closer to achieving genuine gender equality and social inclusivity.

Inclusion of LGBTQ+¹ Community and Live-in Relationships in the UCC:

In India, the legality of second marriages varies depending on the personal laws of different religious communities. Although under the Special Marriage Act, second marriages after the termination of a previous marriage are legal. As for live-in relationships, they are not illegal, and the judiciary provides some protection to partners involved through judicial interpretations (Basu, 2022). As the UCC aims to replace religious-based laws with a unified set of laws for all citizens, potentially standardising marriage and relationship laws across different religions, it remains a topic of debate and concern since it has yet to define these concepts explicitly.

Responding to the questions raised about LGBTQ+ rights and live-in relationships in Uttarakhand's proposed UCC, Justice (retired) Ranjana Prakash Desai emphasised that the primary goal is ensuring equality and dignity for all society. She stated that the UCC draft has considered the rights of the LGBTQ+ community. However, they will not be included in the recommendations until the Supreme Court delivers its verdict on the legal recognition of same-sex marriage in India.

During their deliberations, the expert panel addressed crucial issues such as setting a uniform age for marriage, acknowledging live-in relationships and the status of children born from such unions, streamlining marriage registration procedures, determining the age of consent for sexual relations, and addressing the matter of early-age childbearing (India Today, 2023).

The anticipated draft of the UCC has sparked significant interest among citizens keen to participate in further discussions and contribute to refining the proposed code. The anticipation reflects people's eagerness to actively engage in the deliberation process and collaboratively improve the UCC to uphold the values of justice and inclusivity.

Approaches to Address the Uniform Civil Code: Perspectives and Possible Solutions

The Centre for Development Policy and Practice discussed India's Uniform Civil Code (UCC) to explore its advantages, challenges, and socioeconomic and cultural implications. The event brought together various participants, including scholars, journalists, industrialists, and activists. The discussion emphasised the importance of inclusive dialogues in shaping policies that cater to the needs of India's religiously and culturally diverse population.

Preserving Cultural Diversity as an asset for India's Progress: The first viewpoint raised during the discussion was that the rationale behind the UCC should be based on something other than an overly strict and

homogenising framework. India's cultural diversity is an asset that should be celebrated and preserved, as it is intertwined with human capital development and progress. Overemphasising homogenisation risks stifling societal growth, and it is crucial to recognise that this misconception often targets Muslims in a politically motivated manner. Preserving diversity is essential for India's overall development and should not be sacrificed for uniformity.

Perspectives on Reforms in Indian Muslim Personal Law: While speaking about reforming Indian Muslim Personal Law, it was suggested that the Muslim community should critically evaluate the evolution of their religious laws and consider reforms. Multiple interpretations exist within religious texts, and some perspectives are imposed on individuals. Muslim scholars should engage in critical thinking and work toward reducing internal tensions within the community. Professor Faizan Mustafa, an Indian academic and legal scholar, emphasised the relatively limited number of laws explicitly mentioned in the Quran and that Muslim law is predominantly shaped through interpretation and the extraction of principles from the Sunnah (teachings and practices of Prophet Muhammad). During the discussion, quoting Allama Iqbal, Prof. Mustafa suggested revisiting the Quranic verses, emphasising the importance of distinguishing between moral and legal commandments for continuous updating and independent legal reasoning within Muslim law.

Certain practices like polygamy and Halala, which have demonstrated negative consequences for the well-being of Muslims in India, deserve special attention for re-evaluation. On a positive note, certain aspects of Muslim personal laws, such as inheritance laws, are more progressive and fairer than commonly perceived. However, it is crucial to acknowledge that patriarchal practices within the Muslim community have hindered gender equality. Therefore, it becomes imperative to prioritise discussions on these intricate issues and emphasise the values of liberty and equality when formulating new legislation.

Handling the UCC with Caution: Another perspective highlighted the urgency created during this discourse. The discussion on UCC requires careful consideration, and any sudden reaction with little thought could be concerning. The UCC can be seen as a political strategy aimed at mobilising the masses. There is a need to avoid excessive politicisation of the UCC, as overemphasising the UCC may deepen divisions between Hindus and Muslims, which could be advantageous for specific political agendas.

Broadening the UCC perspective for other religious and tribal communities is also required as it is crucial to consider the perspectives and concerns of other religious and ethnic communities, as limited engagement between various

stakeholders might potentially lead to the imposition of Hindu laws on all individuals in the long run.

Another concern raised during this discussion was the politicisation of the UCC as a women's issue for vote bank politics. While reforming Muslim personal laws is necessary, the current political agenda may be misinterpreted as genuine change, particularly by women who have experienced religious-based discrimination. It is, therefore, essential to handle the issue of the UCC with caution and initiate comprehensive dialogues that include people from different backgrounds. An inclusive platform for discussion will ensure that the UCC addresses the diverse needs and interests of the population without perpetuating injustice or disregarding individual rights and identities.

Learning from past shortcomings, it was recognised that a calibrated and careful approach is necessary when dealing with religious issues, as demonstrated by cases like Shah Bano and the Babri Masjid controversy. Rejecting the UCC outright is not a solution; fostering a culture of open debate and discussion is essential.

Role of Muslim Board and Emphasis on Fair and Impartial Court

System: The role and authority of the All-India Muslim Personal Law Board were also questioned, mainly since Indian courts already handle civil cases related to marriage, divorce, and inheritance. Evaluating the board's responsibilities and interpretation of laws can contribute to a more transparent discussion and potentially lead to reforms.

In a comparative analysis of Western and Islamic law, it becomes evident that they diverge significantly in their fundamental approach. The Western legal system primarily revolves around the formulation of laws, which are subsequently subject to interpretation by courts. Conversely, the Islamic legal framework operates on a distinct paradigm where the primary focus lies in interpreting the sources before the actual formation of laws. In this context, interpretation assumes precedence over the legislative process.

Prof. Mustafa placed a greater emphasis on establishing a fair and impartial court system as a priority. He argued against religion being the sole basis for the Constitution, advocating for a more nuanced approach that is more comprehensive regarding its inclusivity.

Embracing Constructive Dialogue and Unity: The discussion concluded on the note that solidarity among citizens is vital to navigating the complexities of the UCC. A more comprehensive and balanced approach can be achieved by promoting constructive dialogue, setting aside personal differences, and incorporating diverse voices. It is crucial to foster a sense of unity and create a platform for open discussions that collectively address

concerns, leading to decisions that uphold justice, equality, and the well-being of all individuals in India's diverse society. This discussion effectively presented a diverse range of beliefs, instilling a sense of hope and assuring everyone that there is still room for open dialogue and constructive engagement.

Way Forward

In recent news, the Law Commission of India has extended the deadline for public responses on the Uniform Civil Code (UCC) until July 28 after receiving an overwhelming response and numerous requests for an extension. This extension allows a broader range of stakeholders to contribute their views and suggestions on the significant topic of the Uniform Civil Code. It demonstrates that the debate surrounding the Indian UCC remains a complex and contentious issue that requires thoughtful consideration and inclusive dialogue.

Given the widespread attention to this matter, it is crucial to address it pragmatically and with sensitivity, considering the viewpoints and worries of all societal segments. Developing a just and forward-thinking Uniform Civil Code requires seeking common ground that upholds principles of justice, equality, and inclusivity while still honouring the diverse religious landscape of India. As dialogues progress, striking a balance between preserving cultural identities and promoting a unified legal framework becomes paramount, reflecting the vision of a harmonious and united nation.

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